

Psychological Burden of Hidradenitis Suppurativa: A Cross-Sectional Study of Distress, Anxiety and DepressionDebatraya Paul¹, Srikrishna Prasad Panda², Karthi Kishore³, Vikas Pathania⁴, Santanu Banerjee⁵, Abhay Singh⁶¹MD, DNB, Dermatologist, Dept of Dermatology, MH Jaipur, India²MD, DNB, Assistant Professor, Dept of Psychiatry, Armed Forces Medical College Pune, India³MD, Dermatologist, Dept of Dermatology, Military Hospital, Shillong, India⁴Prof & HOD, Dept of Dermatology, Base Hospital, Lucknow, India⁵HOD, Dept of Dermatology, MH Jaipur, India⁶DNB Dermatologist, Dept of Dermatology, MH Jaipur, India

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Corresponding author: Dr. Srikrishna Prasad Panda

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Abstract**Background:** Hidradenitis suppurativa is a chronic, inflammatory, disfiguring dermatological disorder, recalcitrant to treatment and hampers the mental condition of the patients. This study attempted to access the common psychiatric comorbidities in patients of Hidradenitis suppurativa.**Methods:** 60 patients of Hidradenitis suppurativa were recruited through purposive sampling. Hidradenitis suppurativa was staged according to Hurley Staging. Self-report data was gathered using standardized questionnaires for psychological distress, depression and anxiety. Statistical analysis was conducted to examine correlations between these psychosocial variables and the degree of marital discord.**Results:** Half of our patients had significant psychological distress as evidenced by GHQ-12 scores. 46.7% of our patients scored above cut off for both anxiety and depression subscale of HADS. There was significant association between Hurley stage of illness and the presence of psychological distress, including anxiety and depression.**Conclusion:** The strong association between disease severity and the prevalence of psychological distress, anxiety and depression calls for a comprehensive and multidisciplinary approach to patient care. By recognizing the significant mental health challenges faced by HS patients, healthcare providers can develop targeted interventions that address both the physical and emotional aspects of the disease.**Keywords:** Hidradenitis suppurativa, Depression, Anxiety, Psychiatric morbidity in Hidradenitis suppurativa.

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Introduction

Hidradenitis suppurativa (HS) is a chronic inflammatory, disfiguring dermatosis which affects the apocrine glands of the body, predominant site of the body being axilla, chest and buttocks. It is characterized by recurrent abscess formation, nodules, sinuses formation and ultimately heals with scarring. [1]

HS may develop during adolescence, however, it usually manifest after puberty. The world prevalence of HS ranges between 0.00033% - 4.1%, with a period prevalence (2007-2016) of 0.06% in Asian population. [2] However data on HS prevalence in India is not available. Dysfunctional immune response leading to chronic inflammation and occlusion of apocrine glands is the mainstay of pathogenesis along with contribution of local microbiome. Patients with HS

have a significantly reduced quality of life due to both physical and psychological discomfort related to the disease. The patients with HS are found to have increased tendency to develop psychiatric comorbidities such as depression, anxiety, schizophrenia, bipolar disorders etc. [3] The exact reason for the prevalence of psychiatric disease in patients with HS is not properly understood.

Pro inflammatory cytokines like tumour necrosis factor-alpha and interleukin-10 can attribute to the pathogenesis of HS and psychiatric disorders. [4,5] Although literature review establishes the association of psychological issues with HS [6,7], there is no such study which has been performed on the population of Indian subcontinent. The aim of our study is to highlight the psychiatric comorbidities prevalent in HS patients in a tertiary

care hospital in the western part of Indian subcontinent.

Materials and Methods

Sample and procedure: The HS patients who attended the Dermatology OPD of a tertiary care hospital between Jan 2023 to Dec 2023 was included in the study after obtaining informed consent.

The study included all clinically diagnosed cases of HS who were > 14 years of age. Patients who were medically too ill to participate in the interview were excluded. Subjects who were having dementia, active psychotic symptoms and those with h/o delusional disorders were excluded. Identity of the participants was kept confidential.

The assessment was carried out based on self-reported questionnaires. All guidelines as per declaration of Helsinki and good clinical practice guidelines were followed in the study.

Measures

Sociodemographic questionnaire: Demographic & clinical profile of the patients including age, sex, employment status, family h/o of HS, smoking & alcohol intake status, BMI, sites of body involvement, concomitant presence of acne vulgaris were recorded.

Hurley Staging: The Hurley staging system for Hidradenitis Suppurativa introduced by Dr. Herbert Hurley in 1989 was used in this study to assess the severity and progression of the disease. Stage I represents single or multiple abscesses without sinus tracts or scarring. In stage II there are recurrent abscesses with sinus tracts and scarring, but widely separated lesions. Stage III represents multiple interconnected sinus tracts and abscesses across a large area, leading to severe scarring. [8]

General Health Questionnaire (GHQ-12): GHQ is a self-administered screening questionnaire which has been widely used to detect non-psychotic psychiatric disturbances in a variety of settings. Patients were screened for psychological distress using this 12 item scale. A cut off score of 2 was taken to assess the mental well-being in present study. [9]

Hospital and Depression Scale (HADS): The Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS) is a 14-item self-report screening scale that was originally developed to indicate the possible presence of anxiety and depressive states in the setting of a medical out-patient clinic. It contains two 7 item scales: one for anxiety and one for depression both with a score range of 0–21. Each of the items can be scored from 0 to 3 based on severity of distress. A cut off score of ≥ 8 was fixed for anxiety or depression. [10]

Figure 1: Clinical images of Hidradenitis Suppurativa involving various body sites

Statistical Analysis: Our data contains information about 60 patients which includes both categorical and continuous data. Continuous data were presented as means with standard deviations (SD) or median with interquartile range (Q1-Q3), and range, and categorical data as numbers with percentages. The relationships between Hurley stage and all explanatory variables were examined with ANOVA and Fisher Exact test for association. All statistical analyses were computed using IBM SPSS statistics version 23 (SPSS, Inc., Chicago, IL, USA).

Results

In our study 78 patients were approached during the study period, however 10 patients did not provide consent and were excluded. Amongst the rest, 8 patients did not meet the eligibility criteria. We are presenting here the data of 60 patients. The median age of patients with Hurley stage I was 24 years, and for stage II and III were 20 years and 21 years, respectively. On the other hand, the median age of onset of HS decreased with increasing Hurley stage, i.e. 22 years for Hurley stage I, 18 years for stage II, and 16.5 years for stage III. The frequency of Hurley stage was found to be more in females than in males, where 80% females were

found with stage II and 30.8% males were found with stage I. The employment status showed that 80% students mostly had Hurley stage II, 38.5% working patients, 7.7% patients having business and housewives had stage I. About 26.7% patients gave history of first degree relative with HS, whereas 73.3% patients did not have any first degree relative with HS. [Figure 1 Clinical images of Hidradenitis Suppurativa involving various body sites]. Relation of patient characteristics with Hurley stages mentioned in Table 1.30 patients (50%) had significant psychological distress as per GHQ-12 scores.

All patients in Hurley Stage 3 had significant psychological distress. The comparison of Hurley stages with GHQ-12 scores is depicted in Figure 2. 46.7% of study participants had significant anxiety symptoms, scored above cut off in Anxiety subscale. The comparison of Hurley stages with HADS Anxiety subscale in depicted in Figure 3. 30.8% of participants in Hurley stage 1 had anxiety symptoms, where as it was 53.3% and 100% for stage 2 and stage 3 respectively. 26 (46.7%) patients had HADS scores above cut off for depression. The comparison of Hurley stages with HADS Depression subscale is depicted in Figure 4.

Table 1: Relation of patient characteristics with Hurley stage

	Hurley Stage			Total (N = 30)	p-value
	I (N = 13)	II (N = 15)	III (N = 2)		
Age, years					0.34
Median (Q1-Q3)	24 (19-28)	20 (18-24)	21 (18-24)	21.5 (18-26.25)	
Range	17-32	14-29	15-27	14-32	
Age of onset of HS, years					0.18
Median (Q1-Q3)	22 (18-24)	18 (16-20)	16.5 (14.75-18.25)	19 (16-23.25)	
Range	16-30	13-33	13-20	13-33	
Gender					0.07
Female	9 (69.2)	12 (80)	0 (0)	21 (70)	
Male	4 (30.8)	3 (20)	2 (100)	9 (30)	
Employment status					0.38
Student	6 (46.2)	12 (80)	1 (50)	19 (63.3)	
Working	5 (38.5)	2 (13.3)	1 (50)	8 (26.7)	
Business	1 (7.7)	1 (6.7)	0 (0)	2 (6.7)	
Housewife	1 (7.7)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (3.3)	
1st degree relative with HS					1
Yes	4 (30.8)	4 (26.7)	0 (0)	8 (26.7)	
No	9 (69.2)	11 (73.3)	2 (100)	22 (73.3)	
BMI					0.61
<20	1 (7.7)	3 (20)	1 (50)	5 (16.7)	
20-24	5 (38.5)	7 (46.7)	0 (0)	12 (40)	
25-29	4 (30.8)	3 (20)	1 (50)	8 (26.7)	
30-34	3 (23.1)	2 (13.3)	0 (0)	5 (16.7)	
Smoking					0.56
Current	2 (15.4)	2 (13.3)	1 (50)	5 (16.7)	
Former	3 (23.1)	2 (13.3)	0 (0)	5 (16.7)	
Never	8 (61.5)	11 (73.3)	1 (50)	20 (66.7)	
Alcohol					0.78

Yes	2 (15.4)	4 (26.7)	0 (0)	6 (20)	
No	11 (84.6)	11 (73.3)	2 (100)	24 (80)	
Site of involvement					0.08
Chest	0 (0)	2 (13.3)	0 (0)	2 (6.7)	
Axilla	12 (92.3)	8 (53.3)	1 (50)	21 (70)	
Buttocks	0 (0)	1 (6.7)	0 (0)	1 (3.3)	
Chest + Axilla	0 (0)	4 (26.7)	1 (50)	5 (16.7)	
Axilla + Buttock	1 (7.7)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (3.3)	
Acne Vulgaris					0.001*
I	0 (0)	1 (6.7)	0 (0)	1 (3.3)	
II	0 (0)	3 (20)	0 (0)	3 (10)	
III	0 (0)	3 (20)	1 (50)	4 (13.3)	
IV	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (50)	1 (3.3)	
No	13 (100)	8 (53.3)	0 (0)	21 (70)	
GHQ 12 Score					0.3
2 or less	6(46.2)	9 (60)	0 (0)	15 (50)	
3 or more	7 (53.8)	6 (40)	2 (100)	15 (50)	
HADS Score					
Anxiety subscale					0.22
Median (Q1-Q3)	6 (3-9)	7 (2-10.5)	13 (13-13)	6 (2.75-11.5)	
Range	0-15	0-17	13-13	0-17	
Depression subscale					0.47
Median (Q1-Q3)	4 (1-10)	6 (2-9)	10 (8-12)	6 (1-9.25)	
Range	15-Jan	0-13	14-Jun	0-15	
Categorical variables are number (percentage), continuous variables are median (first quartile-third quartile) and range.					

Figure 2: Comparison between Hurley stage (I vs. II vs. III) and GHQ-12 score (normal vs. abnormal) based on frequencies

Figure 3: Comparison between Hurley stage (I vs. II vs. III) and HADS-Anxiety subscale (normal vs. abnormal) based on frequencies

Figure 4. Comparison between Hurley stage (I vs. II vs. III) and HADS-Depression subscale (normal vs. abnormal) based on frequencies

Discussion

Hidradenitis suppurativa is a chronic inflammatory disorder where associated psychological burden plays a very crucial role. The intractable nature of HS and its association with pain, suppuration, impaired daily activities and malodour causes both physical and psychological discomfort, but also significantly impaired quality of life. [11] our study, we measured psychological distress by GHQ - 12. Our study results demonstrate a significant

association between the severity of Hidradenitis suppurativa (HS), as classified by the Hurley staging system, and the presence of psychological distress, including anxiety and depression.

The data indicate that 50% of the patients exhibited significant psychological distress, with all patients in Hurley Stage 3 experiencing this condition. This finding suggests a direct correlation between increasing disease severity and the worsening of mental health outcomes. The high prevalence of

psychological distress among HS patients, as evidenced by GHQ-12 scores, is consistent with existing literature. For example, Matusiak et al. (2010) reported that HS is often accompanied by considerable psychiatric comorbidities, including depression and anxiety. [12] Kouris et al. also reported that HS patients had higher levels of psychological distress compared to the general population. [13] The current study's finding that half of the participants experienced significant psychological distress further emphasizes the mental health challenges faced by individuals with HS. Notably, the progression to Hurley Stage 3 was universally associated with significant psychological distress, indicating that the physical and emotional burden of the disease intensifies with its severity. This observation aligns with the biopsychosocial model, which points that chronic illnesses like HS can impact multiple aspects of a person's life, including their mental health.

The study also highlights a concerning trend in the prevalence of anxiety symptoms among HS patients. According to the HADS Anxiety subscale, 46.7% of the participants scored above the cut-off, suggesting clinically significant anxiety symptoms. A more granular analysis reveals a stage-wise increase in anxiety prevalence: 30.8% in Hurley Stage 1, 53.3% in Stage 2, and 100% in Stage 3. This escalation in anxiety symptoms with advancing disease severity may be attributed to several factors, including chronic pain, the unpredictability of flare-ups and the social and emotional impacts of visible skin lesions. These findings echo those of Deckers et al., who demonstrated that anxiety disorders are more prevalent among patients with severe HS. [14] A database analysis study conducted in USA recently which analyzed data of 9597 HS patients found that patients of HS have 2.43 times higher risk of developing anxiety disorders than dermatology controls. [15] The constant physical discomfort and social stigma associated with HS likely exacerbate feelings of anxiety, leading to a higher incidence of anxiety disorders as the disease progresses.

The study also reports a notable prevalence of depression among HS patients, with 46.7% scoring above the cut-off on the HADS Depression subscale. Similar to anxiety, the prevalence of depression increased with the severity of HS: 30.8% in Stage 1, 53.3% in Stage 2, and 100% in Stage 3. The correlation between increasing disease severity and higher rates of depression underscores the profound psychological impact of HS. Previous research conducted by Esmann and Jemec has documented the high incidence of depression in patients with chronic dermatological conditions, attributing it to factors such as chronic pain, social isolation, and a diminished quality of life. The physical symptoms of HS, such as recurrent

abscesses and scarring can severely impact patients' self-esteem and body image, contributing to the development of depressive symptoms. Moreover, the chronic nature of the disease, coupled with the lack of a definitive cure, can lead to feelings of hopelessness and despair, further exacerbating depression. Higher prevalence of depressive symptoms can also be explained by inflammatory nature of the illness leading to higher circulating pro inflammatory cytokines which itself is an independent risk factor for depressive symptoms. [16]

The findings from this study underscore the critical need for a holistic approach to managing HS, encompassing both physical and mental health care. The high prevalence of psychological distress, anxiety and depression among patients, particularly those in advanced stages of the disease, highlights the importance of integrated care strategies which should include mental health professionals. Dermatologists should consider regular psychological assessments and early intervention as essential components of HS management. This comprehensive approach can help identify patients at risk of developing psychiatric comorbidities and provide them with the necessary support. Furthermore, interdisciplinary collaboration between dermatologists, mental health professionals and other healthcare providers is crucial to address the multifaceted challenges faced by HS patients. Interventions could include cognitive-behavioural therapy, psycho-education and support groups to help patients cope with the psychological impact of the disease.

The study's findings might be limited by the sample size, potentially limiting the generalizability of the results to other groups or settings. This study being cross sectional, cannot establish a causal relationship. Longitudinal studies would be needed to determine if HS progression directly leads to worsening psychological outcomes over time. The use of self-reported measures like the GHQ-12 and HADS may introduce bias, as participants might underreport or over report their symptoms due to stigma or personal perceptions. This could affect the accuracy of the psychological distress assessment. Addressing these limitations in future research could help strengthen the evidence on the psychological impact of HS and improve patient care strategies.

Conclusion

This study adds to the growing body of evidence on the psychological burden associated with HS. The strong association between disease severity and the prevalence of psychological distress, anxiety and depression calls for a comprehensive and multidisciplinary approach to patient care. By recognizing the significant mental health

challenges faced by HS patients, healthcare providers can develop targeted interventions that address both the physical and emotional aspects of the disease. Further research is needed to explore the underlying mechanisms linking HS severity with psychological outcomes and to develop effective treatments that improve the overall quality of life for these patients.

References

1. Esmann S, Jemec GBE. Psychosocial impact of hidradenitis suppurativa: a qualitative study. *Acta Derm Venereol.* 2011 May; 91(3):328–32.
2. Chandran NS, Lee JH, Kurokawa I. Hidradenitis suppurativa in South-East Asia and East Asia. *Exp Dermatol.* 2021 Jun; 30 Suppl 1:23–6.
3. Huilaja L, Tiri H, Jokelainen J, Timonen M, Tasanen K. Patients with Hidradenitis Suppurativa Have a High Psychiatric Disease Burden: A Finnish Nationwide Registry Study. *J Invest Dermatol.* 2018 Jan; 138(1):46–51.
4. Van der Zee HH, de Ruyter L, van den Broecke DG, Dik WA, Laman JD, Prens EP. Elevated levels of tumour necrosis factor (TNF)- α , interleukin (IL)-1 β and IL-10 in hidradenitis suppurativa skin: a rationale for targeting TNF- α and IL-1 β . *Br J Dermatol.* 2011 Jun; 164(6):1292–8.
5. Köhler CA, Freitas TH, Maes M, de Andrade NQ, Liu CS, Fernandes BS, et al. Peripheral cytokine and chemokine alterations in depression: a meta-analysis of 82 studies. *Acta Psychiatr Scand.* 2017 May; 135(5):373–87.
6. Onderdijk AJ, van der Zee HH, Esmann S, Lophaven S, Dufour DN, Jemec GBE, et al. Depression in patients with hidradenitis suppurativa. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol JEADV.* 2013 Apr; 27(4):473–8.
7. Shavit E, Dreiherr J, Freud T, Halevy S, Vinker S, Cohen AD. Psychiatric comorbidities in 3207 patients with hidradenitis suppurativa. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol JEADV.* 2015 Feb; 29(2):371–6.
8. Dagenet CB, De DR, Shih T, Brooks B, Fixsen D, Park SE, et al. Hurley Staging Training for Hidradenitis Suppurativa Patients. *Skin Appendage Disord.* 2024 Jul 12; 1–4.
9. Goldberg DP, Hillier VF. A scaled version of the General Health Questionnaire. *Psychol Med.* 1979; 9(1):139–45.
10. Zigmond AS, Snaith RP. The Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale. *Acta Psychiatr Scand.* 1983 Jun; 67(6):361–70.
11. Nguyen TV, Damiani G, Orenstein L a. V, Hamzavi I, Jemec GB. Hidradenitis suppurativa: an update on epidemiology, phenotypes, diagnosis, pathogenesis, comorbidities and quality of life. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol JEADV.* 2021 Jan; 35(1): 50–61.
12. Matusiak Ł, Bieniek A, Szepietowski JC. Hidradenitis suppurativa markedly decreases quality of life and professional activity. *J Am Acad Dermatol.* 2010 Apr; 62(4):706–8, 708.e1.
13. Quality of Life and Psychosocial Implications in Patients with Hidradenitis Suppurativa - PubMed [Internet]. [Cited 2024 Aug 19]. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28052274/>.
14. Deckers IE, Kimball AB. The Handicap of Hidradenitis Suppurativa. *Dermatol Clin.* 2016 Jan; 34(1):17–22.
15. Incidence of anxiety disorder in adults with hidradenitis suppurativa - PubMed [Internet]. [Cited 2024 Aug 19]. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/38564268/>.
16. Frontiers | exploring the role of inflammation in major depressive disorder: beyond the monoamine hypothesis [Internet]. [Cited 2024 Aug 19]. Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/behavioral-neuroscience/articles/10.3389/fnbeh.2023.1282242/full>